

AI-enhanced learning management system

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ABSTRACT: The integration of AI into Learning Management Systems (LMS) has revolutionized the educational landscape. This paper delves into the comprehensive functionalities of an AI-enhanced LMS, aimed at optimizing various aspects of the learning journey. Key features encompass intuitive course browsing and filtering, streamlined course purchases via the Stripe payment gateway, and meticulous tracking of chapter completion status. Additionally, the system incorporates sophisticated algorithms for calculating progress in enrolled courses, enabling learners to monitor their advancement effectively. With a dedicated student dashboard and a dynamic teacher mode, the platform caters to the distinct requirements of both learners and educators. Teachers can effortlessly create and manage courses, chapters, and associated resources, benefitting from features such as drag-and-drop chapter reordering and rich text editing. Leveraging advanced technologies like UploadThing for media uploads and Mux for video processing, the system ensures a seamless user experience. Furthermore, AI is utilized for test and notes features, providing personalized question sets to students during assessments. This study underscores the significance of AI in transforming education delivery and presents a robust framework for AI-driven learning management systems.

Keywords: AI-enhanced Learning Management System, Stripe payment gateway, UploadThing, Mux, Student Dashboard, Teacher Mode, Personalized Learning, Educational Technology.

I. INTRODUCTION

The landscape of education is evolving rapidly, driven by advancements in technology and the ever-growing demand for personalized learning experiences. At the forefront of this transformation lies the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into Learning Management Systems (LMS). An AI-enhanced LMS represents a paradigm shift in how education is delivered, offering a dynamic and adaptive platform that caters to the diverse needs of learners and educators alike.

In today's digital age, access to quality education is no longer confined to traditional classrooms. Instead, learners seek flexible and tailored learning experiences that accommodate their individual preferences, pace, and learning styles. Similarly, educators require tools and resources that enable them to engage students effectively, track progress, and provide timely feedback.

In this context, this paper explores the transformative potential of AI-enhanced LMS in redefining the future of education. By harnessing the power of AI to personalize learning, empower educators, and optimize administrative processes, these systems hold promise for creating inclusive, engaging, and effective learning environments that meet the diverse needs of 21st-century learners.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

1. **Ways and Means of Employing AI Technology in E-Learning Systems :** Employing state-of-the-art artificial intelligence (AI) technology in current e-learning systems can bring personalized, adaptive, and intelligent services to both students and educators. Although we have seen more and more successful applications of AI in e-learning, most of them have not yet been expanded to or adopted in widely used e-learning systems, especially open-source learning management systems (LMS) such as Moodle, Sakai, and so on. This observation takes us to the analysis and discussion of the current work in both LMS and applied AI. The findings include that current intelligent LMS systems are still in their early stage, while AI applications need to handle some problems or be modified before applying them to the LMS systems, and AI technology also needs to be brought to open source communities.
2. **Developing e-learning application specifically designed for learning introductory programming :** This research aims to address the challenges faced by undergraduate students in understanding the fundamental concepts of programming in the Information Technology field. While programming courses are typically taught in classrooms and through Learning Management Systems (LMS) like Moodle, these traditional methods are often too general for

teaching introductory programming. To improve the learning experience, this research proposes an alternative e-learning solution that incorporates interactive multimedia. This e-learning application is designed to enhance the understanding of introductory programming by providing an interactive platform for students to learn independently. All that's required is a web browser and an internet connection on a computer or tablet. The course materials are divided into three categories: multimedia videos, images, and program code. The application delivers results within the same window where users can practice and write code. To ensure efficient access, video content is kept to less than 10 minutes in length, enabling faster downloading and playback.

- 3. User Satisfaction Factors on Learning Management Systems Usage:** The purpose of the research is to determine the factors that affect the satisfaction of the use of Learning Management System, especially by students. Research stages are done through literature based on End-User Computing Satisfaction (EUCS) satisfaction factor which consists of content, accuracy, timeless, ease of use and format. Questionnaires were developed based on each factor of EUCS and distributed to the user ie the students. Based on the formula Izaac and Michael the results of the sample calculation there are 380 students who become sample. Based on data from questionnaires that have been distributed validation test and reliability of 20 data responder first before further processing. The result of the questionnaire that has been collected is analyzed to the gap between expectation and reality to get user satisfaction on the use of LMS.

III. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

1. Question Generation:

Use a pre-trained language model (e.g., BERT, T5, or GPT-3) to generate a set of questions related to the course or document content.

Apply a rule-based algorithm or a machine learning model to filter out irrelevant or redundant questions.

2. Question Selection:

Use a diversity-based algorithm (e.g., Maximal Marginal Relevance or Submodularity) to select a diverse set of questions from the generated question pool.

Ensure that the selected questions cover different aspects and levels of difficulty of the course or document content.

3. Test Administration:

Present the selected questions to the user in a random order.

Allow the user to answer each question and provide feedback (e.g., correct/incorrect, explanation, or reference to the course or document).

4. Question Evaluation:

Evaluate the user's answers using a pre-defined scoring function (e.g., accuracy, completeness, or relevance).

Provide the user with a score and feedback on their performance.

IV. DATASETS

Data Structures and Algorithms (DSA)

- Which data structure follows the Last In First Out (LIFO) principle?
 - A) Queue
 - B) Stack
 - C) Linked List
 - D) Heap
- What is the time complexity of searching an element in a binary search tree?
 - A) $O(1)$
 - B) $O(\log n)$
 - C) $O(n)$
 - D) $O(n \log n)$
- Which sorting algorithm has the best time complexity in the worst-case scenario?
 - A) Bubble Sort
 - B) Merge Sort
 - C) Quick Sort
 - D) Insertion Sort
- In Dijkstra's algorithm, what data structure is typically used to implement the priority queue?
 - A) Array
 - B) Linked List
 - C) Heap
 - D) Stack
- Which data structure is suitable for implementing a hash table?
 - A) Array
 - B) Stack
 - C) Queue
 - D) Binary Tree
- Which of the following is not a fundamental operation in a stack data structure?
 - A) Push
 - B) Pop
 - C) Peek
 - D) Delete
- What is the space complexity of a recursive algorithm with $O(n)$ time complexity?
 - A) $O(1)$

FIG 1

Javascript

- What does the typeof operator in JavaScript return for a variable declared with the const keyword?
- A) "object"
 - B) "function"
 - C) "undefined"
 - D) "string"
- Which function is used to add an element to the end of an array in JavaScript?
- A) push()
 - B) add()
 - C) insert()
 - D) append()
- What does the NaN global property represent in JavaScript?
- A) "Not a Number"
 - B) "Null or Not Defined"
 - C) "Negative Infinity"
 - D) "Not Available"
- What is the result of 3 + '3' in JavaScript?
- A) 6
 - B) "33"
 - C) "6"
 - D) Error
- Which of the following is not a valid JavaScript variable name?
- A) myVariable
 - B) \$myVariable
 - C) _myVariable
 - D) myVariable
- What is the output of console.log(typeof null) in JavaScript?
- A) "null"
 - B) "object"
 - C) "undefined"
 - D) "string"
- What does the === operator check for in JavaScript?
- A) Value equality

FIG 2

ReactJS

- Which lifecycle method is called immediately after a component is rendered?
 - A) componentWillMount()
 - B) componentDidMount()
 - C) componentWillUnmount()
 - D) componentDidUpdate()
- What is ReactJS?
 - A) A JavaScript framework for building user interfaces
 - B) A server-side scripting language
 - C) A database management system
 - D) A styling library
- Which of the following is not a valid way to define a component in React?
 - A) Functional component
 - B) Class component
 - C) Stateless component
 - D) Renderless component
- What is JSX in ReactJS?
 - A) JavaScript External XML
 - B) JavaScript XML
 - C) JavaScript Extension
 - D) JavaScript XHR
- What is the purpose of ReactJS's setState() method?
 - A) To update the state of a component
 - B) To render the component
 - C) To define props
 - D) To define state
- Which React lifecycle method is invoked before a component is unmounted and destroyed?
 - A) componentWillUnmount()
 - B) componentDidMount()
 - C) componentWillUpdate()
 - D) componentWillReceiveProps()
- What is the purpose of keys in React lists?

FIG 3

We are gathering datasets from multiple sources to build comprehensive collections for Data Structures and Algorithms (DSA), JavaScript, and ReactJS. These datasets are organized into three distinct directories: Train, Valid, and Test, each containing a variety of resources relevant to the respective topic. The Train directory comprises a substantial dataset of 5.3 GB, while the Valid directory holds 824.5 MB of data, and the Test directory contains 5.1 GB of resources.

V. METHODOLOGY

1. Requirement Gathering and Analysis:

Conduct a thorough analysis of the project requirements, including all features listed.

Define user stories and use cases to capture the expected behavior and interactions of users with the system. Prioritize features based on importance and feasibility for the initial release.

2. Technology Stack Selection:

Choose appropriate technologies and frameworks to build the Learning Management System (LMS) and associated features. Consider factors such as scalability, security, and compatibility with desired functionalities.

3. Database Design and Integration:

Design the database schema to support features such as course management, chapter organization, user authentication, progress tracking, and content storage. Integrate PostgreSQL as the database management system, leveraging Prisma for ORM functionalities.

4. User Authentication and Authorization:

Implement user authentication using Clerk for seamless and secure login/signup processes.

Define roles (e.g., student, teacher) and permissions to manage access to different features and functionalities.

5. Course Management:

Develop functionalities to allow teachers to create new courses and chapters.

Implement drag-and-drop functionality to enable easy reordering of chapters within a course.

Integrate UploadThing for uploading thumbnails, attachments, and videos associated with each chapter.

6. Payment Gateway Integration:

Integrate Stripe payment gateway to facilitate course purchases securely.

Implement features to browse and filter courses based on various criteria such as category, price, and popularity.

7. Progress Tracking and Student Dashboard:

Develop functionalities to mark chapters as completed or uncompleted by students.

Calculate and display progress for each course on the student dashboard.

Provide insights into completed chapters, upcoming chapters, and overall course progress.

8. Content Management and Presentation:

Utilize a rich text editor to allow teachers to add descriptive content for each chapter.

Implement HLS video player using Mux for seamless playback of video content within chapters.

9. AI Integration for Test and Notes Features:

Implement AI algorithms to generate new sets of questions for tests, ensuring uniqueness and relevance for each student.

Develop functionalities for students to take tests and make notes within the platform.

10. Testing and Quality Assurance:

Conduct rigorous testing of the developed features to ensure functionality, performance, and security.

Perform user acceptance testing (UAT) to gather feedback and refine the system based on user input.

11. Deployment and Maintenance:

Deploy the system on a secure and scalable infrastructure.

Provide ongoing maintenance and support to address any issues and incorporate new features or enhancements based on user feedback.

VI. RESULTS

Course Management:

- Users can browse, filter, and purchase courses using the integrated Stripe payment gateway.

Progress Tracking:

- Students can mark chapters as completed/uncompleted, and progress is calculated for each course.

User Dashboards:

- Personalized dashboards for students and teachers provide easy access to course content and management tools.

Content Creation:

- Teachers can create courses and chapters, reorder content, and upload multimedia using UploadThing.

Video Playback:

- Mux integration enables smooth video processing and playback with an HLS video player.

Text Editing:

- A rich text editor allows for detailed chapter descriptions and content formatting.

Authentication & Database:

- Secure authentication via Clerk and ORM with Prisma ensure safe user access and efficient data management in PostgreSQL.

AI Feature:

- AI generates unique test questions, and students can take tests within the platform.

Fig 6.1 Login Page

Fig 6.2 Student Dashboard

Fig 6.4 Video Playback

Fig 6.5 Add Notes

Fig 6.6 Add Courses

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The completed Learning Management System (LMS) offers a comprehensive platform for students and teachers to engage in effective learning and teaching experiences. Through intuitive course management functionalities, robust progress tracking mechanisms, and seamless content creation tools, the LMS ensures an enriching educational journey for all users. Integration with secure authentication and database management systems ensures data integrity and user privacy. The incorporation of advanced AI features further enhances the learning experience, providing personalized assessments and note-taking capabilities. Overall, the LMS represents a significant step towards modernizing education delivery and fostering a collaborative learning environment.

Future Work:

In the future, the LMS can be further enhanced with the following features:

1. **AI Chatbot Integration:** Implement an AI-powered chatbot to provide instant assistance, answer queries, and offer personalized recommendations to users, enhancing user engagement and support.
2. **Integrated IDE (Integrated Development Environment):** Integrate an IDE directly into the platform, allowing students to practice coding exercises, debug programs, and collaborate on coding projects within the LMS environment.
3. **Discord Community Integration:** Establish a Discord community for students and teachers to connect, collaborate, and share resources in real-time, fostering a sense of belonging and community engagement.

By incorporating these additional features, the LMS can further enhance its functionality, user engagement, and collaborative learning opportunities, ultimately providing a more holistic and immersive educational experience for all stakeholders.

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